

HIGHLY INTELLECTUAL YOUNG PEOPLE AND THEIR ROLE IN SOCIETY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: In this article, there is a consistent scientific analysis of young people with high intellectual potential, who selflessly serve the country, and their role in the development of society.

Key words: education, young generation, intellect, healthy and spiritually mature, spirituality, morals

Since the first period when the Republic of Uzbekistan gained its independence, special attention has been paid to the youth group, which is the main part of the country. We know well from history that the continuation of any society depends on its successors. In this regard, the leader of our country said, "It is taken from inside any fortress. So we have to make the inside strong. For this, we must sow seeds of loyalty to the country, love for history, and hope for the future in the hearts of young people" [1] - he says.

In this sense, after gaining independence, it is the first task to deliver high-potential personnel suitable for this time and to train them. Today, funds directed to the field of education and science should serve as a solid foundation for the formation of a society with high intellectual potential of the young generation, which is the owner of our country. In order to train such young personnel, it is necessary to establish good relations with foreign countries in the field of science and education and to implement certain reforms. It would be appropriate if we cite the following Decree of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 7, 1997 as an example [2]:

Considering that intelligent, well-rounded national personnel educated on the basis of world standards will make a great contribution to the implementation of socio-political, spiritual and economic reforms in our country, we wish to serve the country selflessly, faithfully, and make it great and powerful. "Mahalla", "Kamolot" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the higher education of our talented young people in order to train talented young men and women who are capable of glorifying the motherland with their talent. , funds like "For a healthy generation" were created and we can see these funds as an important and integral part of the "State policy on youth" implemented in our country. It is necessary to highlight the good works of the foundations in the field of education and the contribution they make to raising the growing generation in a physically healthy and spiritually perfect way.

At the same time, in order to support the immediate successors of the future of our country at the state level, to solve the problems of protecting the interests and rights of young people in a timely manner, to deepen the reforms in the continuous education system, to develop in the real economy and in the spheres of the country's life activities. 2008 is declared as the "Year of Youth" [3] in order to meet the demand for specialists trained by educational institutions and to raise a healthy and well-rounded generation in our country, to realize the creative and intellectual potential of young people. , in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2010, in order to implement large-scale, clearly directed measures to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for the development of the young men and women of our country as well-rounded individuals who fully meet the requirements of the 21st century. The fact that the year was declared as the "Year of the Perfect Generation" [4], we can see how strong the foundation is for building a great future in our country. The issue of raising a highly educated and intellectually mature generation and finding their place in our society, preventing them from falling under the influence of ideas that are foreign to our current identity, has become the most urgent issue of today's era. To this day, we hear and read a lot about the fact that in Uzbekistan, the issues of spirituality and ethics are being widely paid attention to and are being actively applied to life. And now we had the opportunity to see it in action. Their formation allows for deeper mastering of social, economic and legal sciences, solving important problems facing the society, educating not only the specialist, but also the individual. So, the guarantee of development is to support young people, to create opportunities for them. After all, the youth of Uzbekistan is no less than anyone else, as the head of state said.

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